

FOOD POTENTIAL OF THE REGION AND WAYS TO ENSURE THE STABILITY OF PRICES IN THE DOMESTIC MARKET

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Abstract: The effectiveness of the management of the region is largely determined by the system and complexity in the implementation of its development opportunities. One of the ways to achieve this goal is to develop and implement the concept of regional capacity in management. The article considers modern approaches to the definition and classification of the elements of regional potential, and suggests grouping the elements of the region's potential according to the degree of manageability and the nature of the response to the controlling influence. The essence of the economic potential of the region is investigated, taking into account the influence of external factors.

Keywords: regional management, regional potential, economic potential, territorial risks, the level of development of the region.

Introduction. In the field of Agriculture, in order to ensure the stability of prices in the domestic market, it is necessary to take into account the presence of large reserves in food security, food reserves and its economic development, as well as in the development of entrepreneurship.

There are all conditions for the exterioration of not only the internal needs of the region, but also the population of other regions of the Republic and for the reproduction of export-oriented products.

However, on some agricultural products, the extirpation of the population is not satisfied, although the capacity is sufficient, on some types of crops the quality indicators are low in jada.

In order to solve these problems, it is worthwhile to develop entrepreneurship in a wide range by properly organizing work.

Proceeding from the above, the level of satisfaction of the population with rice products in the current year should be increased by 16,6 times or by 51,3 percent compared to the previous year (3%).

To meet this need, it is necessary to organize more than 1244 business entities in the coming years.

In 2021 in the direction of poultry production 75.0 billion. 12 pieces, equivalent to soy, in the direction of fishery 58,0 mlrd. so it is necessary to carry out 32 projects equal to one thousand, 9 equal to 11.1 billion soums in the direction of rabbit breeding, 4 equal to 1.2 billion soums in the direction of beekeeping.

Including,

Table 1

An additional cookie on the need to satisfy the population of the region for food products, improve their quality and enrich the human body with adequate protein.¹

Product type satisfaction	% Lacks	thousand tn required	thousand tn production	the power that must be	established to meet the needs of a thousand
Poultry meat	14,0	28,2	32,8	4,6	9.4 million. general broiler poultry breeding, including 671 thousand head in each district
Fish	25,3	14,1	18,9	4,8	Establishment of an intensive fish lake to 352
Rabbit meat	5,1	7,3	7,7	0,4	1.1 million. feed the head Rabbit, including 76

¹ According to the data of the Main Directorate for economic development and poverty reduction of the surkhandarya region, the author writes.

					thousand birds in a haystack.
Rice	51,3	11,9	24,5	12,6	Organization of the cultivation of 12 thousand tons of rice for an additional 3 thousand hectares
Honey	18,4	3,3	4,0	0,7	Establishment of 163 thousand families of bees, 10 thousand beekeeping clusters in each district
Vegetable oil	63,9	9,1	25,3	16,2	

In addition, with the participation of Rungis Semmaris, the Ministry of Agriculture plans to create and manage a network of eight major Agrologistic centers, the only one in Uzbekistan and Central Asia, in accordance with high international standards, with the participation of Rongis Semmaris.

In each Agrological center of the Bunda, all the necessary facilities are concentrated, which include: cross-docks, trade Pavilions, Hotels, commercial banks and services: sorting, calibration, drying, processing, storage, transportation, delivery, customs clearance, quarantine, food safety certification, expert advice, etc.

For information, an Agro center of 20 hectares will be built in the Surkhandarya region. This center will have the capacity to realize 300 thousand tons of products in one year. Through it, 800 jobs will be created.

In order to ensure food security and to maintain the stability of prices in the domestic markets and to reserve agricultural products, in November 2020, 2021, the main sources of demand and compensation for food of the population for the main types of food products were calculated and a program of measures was developed to create a reserve of the required products and

In a month, according to the program of measures:

10 thousand tons of meat, 2,9 thousand tons of poultry meat, 19,3 thousand tons of flour and 8,2 thousand tons of Carrot products fully provide on account of domestic capacity.

Potatoes, onions, rice products were imported from Samarkand, Jizzakh, Khorezm regions and the Republic of Karakolpakstan, total

Savings to the reserve of 43,2 thousand tons.

From this, 22 thousand tons of potatoes, 11 thousand tons of onions, 6,1 thousand tons of carrots, 4,1 thousand tons of rice will be deposited.

Also far from the Centers of the districts, in 56 mountainous areas 1 103,7 tons of potatoes, 564 tons of onions, 646,1 tons of carrots and

An additional reserve of 143,3 tons of rice products will be created.

253 preparatory organizations are involved in reserve events,

74,1 thousand tons of refrigerated houses with a capacity of 21 thousand tons are prepared for storage by commercial banks mlrd.so m loans are allocated funds.

At present, the fund for food security under the regional administration has been established and is being allocated from local budget funds

5 mlrd.so ' m separated.

Supplier enterprise "Surkhon universal Trade" LLC

5.4 billion. som total 563 tons thereof, 100 tn. rice, 183 tn. vegetable oil, 280 tn. sugar products were collected in the reservation. The need for vegetable oil is 25,5 thousand tons, of which 16,2 thousand tons (63,5 percent) are covered by domestic capacity.

The deficit of 9,3 thousand tons of vegetable oil has been set to be covered from the import account, and 18 units have been imported by enterprises to date

It is envisaged to import 3,6 thousand tons of vegetable oil.

The need for sugar is 16 thousand tons, 2,6 thousand tons per month.

Sugar products are brought from domestic enterprises, at the same time, 2 imported 614 tons of sugar were imported by the importer enterprises.

In the peasant markets, constant control over the price of food products is established, in the Department for the fight against economic crimes of the Prosecutor General's office, the "Kol-Centr" is established.

The problems that have arisen are being solved in a timely manner.

According to the targeted program of increasing food production - for 3 years:

629 projects have been launched, 2 trillion 241 mlrd. so mlik loans are allocated, 12 thousand hectares of land are allocated.

As a result of:

27,4 thousand head breeds of cattle were brought, 1,5 million were brought.

Prime poultry,

1 thousand hectares of additional fishing area, capacity in the refrigerator

Increased by 25,1 thousand tons.

The level of satisfaction of the extirpation of the population:

poultry meat from 8,0% – to 14,1%, eggs from 86,7% - to 102,0%, fish from 21,0 % to 47,0%, rice from 19,0% – to 51,0% ,

Also, meat to 106,8%, milk to 238,7%, vegetables

To 216,2%, to 688,5% of melons, to 108% of legumes are covered with excess.

In the spring of next year, savbzavot crops were planted in the method of ninety-nine thousand hectares of land on 40,9 thousand hectares of land in order to meet the demand of the population for food products, to prevent the growth in the price of food products.

Of this, onions 11,5 thousand, carrots 6,2 thousand, beets 1,3 thousand, Greens 13,1 thousand, cabbage 8,8 thousand.

Tirishga special attention is paid to the increase in the number of food products in the future by mastering the lands that have gone out of circulation.

In 2021, 22,5 thousand, of which 12,1 thousand are water-bearing, 10,4 thousand are land-bearing lalmi.

642 ha vegetables, 1117 ha melons, 202 ha potatoes, 1,5 thousand ha soybeans, 3,0 thousand ha fodder crops, 4,2 thousand ha leguminous crops, 350 ha of oil crops, 875 ha of medicinal plants are planted, 9.2 thousand bağzorlar, 1,3 thousand bağzorlar are organized.

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